

The Construction of MIRO – *Multi-model Interreligious Roleplay Outputs*

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Abstract

This working paper documents the construction of MIRO (Multi-model Interreligious Roleplay Outputs), a dataset designed to be used in exploring the capacities of Large Language Models (LLMs) to produce theology — statements committing to a position within a religious tradition — rather than generic, balanced knowledge about religions. Four LLMs (OpenAI's GPT-4o and GPT-5, Anthropic's Claude Sonnet 4, and Google's Gemini 2.5 Flash) were queried both through their APIs and through their proprietary web interfaces. To elicit committed theological output, the models were prompted to roleplay twelve personas — six Christian and six Muslim — spanning a baseline lay believer, historically grounded individual figures, and tradition-specific scholarly or movement positions. All personas were asked the same question: to outline their view on other religions. Persona descriptions were kept deliberately minimal, so that the theological substance of each

response can be attributed to the models' own elaboration from training data rather than to detailed prompting. The paper sets out the rationale behind the choice of models, channels, prompt design and personas, and reflects on the methodological trade-offs involved. MIRO is intended as a shared resource for interdisciplinary analysis of how generative AI mimics contemporary theological discourse, and of the patterns and biases such mimicry reveals.

Keywords: Large Language Models; roleplay; interreligious dialogue; dataset construction; AI-generated theology; Islam; Christianity; MIRO.

AI Contribution Disclosure

This document is published as part of the Non-Human Islam Working Paper Series. All working papers in this series carry an explicit record of how they were produced, and the role of generative AI in the process.

Contribution category: Human-authored AI-assisted

AI system used: Claude Sonnet 4.7, Anthropic

Human authors and their role: Ahmad Kamal, Helena Lipková, Kerstin Radde-Antweiler, Jonas Svensson — conceived and conducted the study; paper authored collaboratively.

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AI contribution: copy-editing and proof reading.

Responsibility statement: Regardless of the degree of AI involvement, the named human authors take full intellectual and ethical responsibility for the content of this paper.

1. Introduction

The object of this working paper is to describe the joint effort of four researchers to collect and structure the dataset *MIRO — Multi-model Interreligious Roleplay Outputs*, the underlying assumptions and the methodological choices made in its construction.

The dataset was constructed to explore to what extent, and in what respects, generative AI, in the form of state-of-the-art Large Language Models (henceforth LLMs), mimics actual, contemporary theological discourse. The question is not whether these systems can mimic religious discourse: that we know. The question concerns the strategic means and quality of the mimicking, when assessed by domain experts, both in information and communication science, and in the study of religions.

2. General Project Information

The dataset was originally constructed to serve two distinct projects.

a. *Human-Centred AI for a Sustainable and Adaptive Society*

HumanAId is a large problem-oriented research project focused on the societal impacts of AI, specifically Large Language Models (LLMs). The project's primary research objectives focus on analyzing the impacts of AI on democratic processes, education, and AI-human communication. The MIRO dataset was generated within the framework of the HumanAId Research Group 3 (RO3: AI-Human Communication Research), which conducts a cross-disciplinary analysis of communicative processes between humans and AI. Its primary goal is to investigate and understand how humans and AI (specifically Generative AI and Large Language Models) interact, interpret one another, and adapt their respective communication patterns. RO3 integrates insights from linguistics, the humanities, social sciences, and technical disciplines to provide a comprehensive mapping of communication dynamics within human-AI systems. The presented project extends the interdisciplinary research outreach to AI-human communication in the domain of religion.

b. *Artificial 'Ulama — biases and patterns in non-human Islam*

This project examines AI-generated Islamic theology, focusing on the responses generated by Large Language Models to prompts relating to Islamic texts, interpretational themes and concepts. The study combines recent theoretical

developments in Islamic studies with issues raised in the field of “explainable AI”, aiming to critically assess how generative AI systems interpret Islam. The project expands the scope of Islamic theological study to include interpretations by non-human entities, systems of generative AI, specifically Large Language Models. It investigates three main areas: Qur’anic interpretation, religious counseling (*fatwa*), and contentious topics in Islamic faith and practice. The goal is to determine the consistency of AI interpretations across different models and compare them with human interpretations. The project ultimately aims to identify and explain any patterns or biases in the AI responses, which could be a result of the training data, computing processes or alignment procedures.¹

2.1 Members of the Team and Their Expertise

Kerstin Radde-Antweiler is a professor of religious studies at the University of Bremen and is part of the Centre for Media, Communication and Information Research. Her research focuses on mediatized religion, video gaming, Pagan and Christian traditions, and ritual studies. A particular emphasis lies on investigating digital religious practices and the communicative construction of religious identity in times of deep mediatization. She researches games as “gameenvironments” — spaces in which meaning, identity, and religious narratives are negotiated. At the moment, she leads an international project on the changing role of religion in societies emerging from Covid-19.

Ahmad M. Kamal is a Senior Lecturer in the Department of Cultural Sciences at Linnaeus University, Växjö, Sweden. Working in the fields of Library and Information Science and the Digital Humanities, Ahmad specializes in the study of information practices, knowledge organization, and digital methods. His current projects include explorations of artificial intelligence for archival collections and historical material.

Helena Lipková is an Assistant Professor at the Department of Information Studies and Librarianship, Faculty of Arts, Charles University, Prague. Her research focuses primarily on information behavior and new media perspectives with a particular emphasis on the domains of religion and spirituality. She examines how contemporary technologies are transforming the communication of information within these fields, specifically exploring their impact on perceptions of trustworthiness, the authority of information sources, and the functioning of online communities. Dr. Lipková currently leads a research team dedicated to

¹ <https://lnu.se/en/research/research-projects/artificial-ulama---patterns-and-biases-in-non-human-islam/>

investigating the dynamics of AI-human communication as part of the HumanAId project.

Jonas Svensson is a Professor in the Study of Religion at Linnaeus University, Växjö, Sweden. He is a trained Islamologist, with a focus on contemporary Muslim religious discourses. He is currently the principal investigator of the above-mentioned project *Artificial 'Ulama*.

3. LLMs and Channels Choice

For the data collection, we selected four different LLMs that at the time of collection were generally agreed upon as being state-of-the-art: OpenAI's GPT-4o and GPT-5, Anthropic's Claude Sonnet 4, and Google's Gemini 2.5 Flash. Originally, only GPT-4o was projected from models provided by OpenAI, but GPT-5 was also included because it was introduced in the midst of data collection, and replaced GPT-4o as the underlying LLM in OpenAI's ChatGPT web application.

Interactions with the chosen LLMs were both programmatic, through the models' API (Application Programming Interface), and through their respective web interface. The data collection via the API was automated through the use of Python scripts and batch processing (responsible collector was Jonas Svensson). The collection via the web interface was manual (performed by Lipková).

The reason for using both “channels” was an expectation of different results. The API calls are “clean” interactions with the model. In the WebUI there may be additional settings introduced, potentially affecting the form and the content of the response. The WebUI is available in the chatbots from OpenAI, Anthropic and Google. However, there is a multitude of chatbots that are constructed by third parties, and that use underlying LLMs from the three large companies, through API calls. It should be noted that these third-party applications do not replicate the “clean” API interaction either. They typically add their own system prompts, settings, and customizations on top of the underlying model, and hence occupy a third position — neither identical to the clean API calls nor to the proprietary WebUIs. This means that the clean API interaction is a baseline that almost no ordinary user ever experiences. If there is already a measurable difference between the responses delivered through the clean API and those delivered through the proprietary WebUIs — where the added layers are presumably relatively modest — then the variation introduced by the considerably more diverse ecosystem of third-party applications is likely even larger, and less

predictable (for Christian examples, see Kurlberg et al. 2026; for Muslim examples, see Wahid 2025). We used the exact same prompt for both the WebUI and the API. Further discussion on the exact mode of interaction with the models will be given below.

4. Prompt Engineering

The joint aim was to probe into the capabilities, tendencies and restrictions of LLMs to produce theology, understood here as statements on what, from an emic, believer’s perspective, constitutes the correct understanding of a religious tradition. This is distinct from knowledge *about* a religion, and the distinction matters methodologically: the results speak to patterns in the systems’ training data and tendencies, not to any individual’s claims *about* what Christianity or Islam authoritatively teaches.

Given the academic background and specialized domain knowledge of Svensson and Radde-Antweiler, the two religious traditions chosen were Islam and Christianity. After reviewing a set of candidate issues within a larger field of religious dialogue and conflict, in line with the overall aim of the project Human-Centred AI for a Sustainable and Adaptive Society, we eventually zoomed in on one: views on other religions.

Since the question concerned the basic capability of the systems to produce theological statements that mimic real-world theological positions in Christianity and Islam, rather than their knowledge of facts about religions, the selection of *which* other religions to ask about was of secondary importance. We settled for a standard list of the large world religions: Christianity, Islam, Judaism, Hinduism and Buddhism. We are aware of the problem of reproducing a “world religion paradigm” (Masuzawa 2005; Owen 2011), with essentialist notions of clear boundaries between, and consistencies within, “religions”, but we also recognize that this paradigm is established in contemporary discourse, and most likely well represented in the LLM training data.

LLMs, or at least the dominant commercially employed LLMs, are generally tuned to be “truthful”, i.e. to deliver factually correct answers to questions. This was, however, not what we were after. In the field of theology, as we use the term and from a humanist researcher’s perspective, there is no one truthful answer to any question, but instead a more or less extensive diversity of perspectives based on different understandings of the religious tradition. This means that a question about “Islam’s view on Christianity” posed to an LLM will typically produce a

generic answer that stresses variation among different Muslim perspectives. Such a response will be “truthful” to some extent, but does not constitute theological output — it does not commit to how adherents to a particular position within a tradition should view other religions.

In order to make the systems produce theological statements, we engaged them in role play (Shanahan 2023). We created a set of six *personas* for Christianity and Islam respectively, and asked the systems to respond strictly in accordance with those *personas*. The choice of the two sets of *personas* was left to the two domain experts, and reflects both some common, and some researcher-specific, interests. The details for each set of *personas* will be given below.

We used one common prompt for all interactions with the LLMs. This was arrived at after extensive testing, evaluation and consequent adjustments:

4.1 The Prompt

This is a task of roleplaying where you adopt a persona.

You are [*persona*]

As a persona, respond strictly within your given role.

1. Provide a well-reasoned answer referencing sources of authority and theological reasoning consistent with the persona.
2. Refrain from referencing other perspectives, engaging in meta-discussion or personal commentary.

Be sure to act your role. Do not deviate from your given persona. Always provide a direct answer, without repeating information on your given role in your answer.

Question: Briefly outline your view on the world religions (Christianity [*for Muslim personas*], Islam [*for Christian personas*], Judaism, Hinduism and Buddhism)

The prompt mirrors both the peculiarities of LLMs as prediction engines and our particular research interests. Several aspects, arrived at after a trial-and-error process, merit comment.

First, we had to be rather firm in stressing the roleplay task and in preventing the LLMs from stepping out of character. LLMs are generally tuned to avoid taking sides or committing to particular positions, and without explicit and repeated instruction to maintain the persona, the systems would tend to break frame and offer meta-commentary or generic overviews — precisely the kind of

response we were trying to move beyond. The redundancy in the prompt (“Be sure to act your role. Do not deviate from your given persona”) was deliberate, and justified by the test runs.

Second, the explicit listing of the five religions — Christianity, Islam, Judaism, Hinduism and Buddhism — was a deliberate choice to ensure comparability across responses. Without it, different personas might address different sets of religions, making systematic comparison difficult.

Third, we wanted the systems to deliver rich answers with details suitable for further analysis, hence the specific demand for a “well-reasoned” answer and references to sources of authority. Test runs showed that responses without these specifications were too generic in character, and provided less material for deeper analysis. It should, however, be noted that the prompt does not specify *which* sources of authority the model should reference. The decision to reference the Bible, church documents, the Qur’an, the ḥadīth, or any other source was made by the models themselves, role-playing their respective personas. This is significant for the analysis that follows.

Fourth, and finally, the prompt explicitly instructs the personas to refrain from referencing other perspectives or engaging in meta-discussion. This was intended to prevent the systems from hedging their theological statements with qualifications about diversity within a tradition — again, the kind of response that a “truthful” LLM naturally gravitates toward, but that would have defeated the purpose of the roleplay design.

4.2 The Personas

Six personas were created for each religious tradition, Christianity and Islam. Initially, we toyed with the idea of creating Muslim and Christian personas that mirrored similar prototypical positions within each tradition. After some attempts, we abandoned this. The two traditions themselves are not straightforwardly symmetrical in their internal divisions, and the specific research interests and competences of the two domain experts did not map neatly onto one another. We did, however, manage to agree on two corresponding personas across both sets.

The first was a generic persona: “a Christian” and “a Muslim” respectively. This was chosen out of a shared interest in having a “baseline” persona whose responses could be compared with those from more constrained, theologically specific personas, in order to detect default tendencies in the models. However, choosing this persona also allows us to observe what the respective LLM

“understands” or “assumes” to be “a Christian” or “a Muslim”. This allows us to draw conclusions about potential biases of the different LLMs and their training data.

The second shared persona type, proposed by Professor Radde-Antweiler, references in each case an actual, albeit deceased, individual whose theological approach is well known and distinct, but also somewhat distanced from the mainstream. The purpose was twofold: to probe the “creativity” of the models in inhabiting a specific, historically grounded voice, and to explore possible limitations in training data.

Beyond these two shared personas, each domain expert constructed the remaining four personas based on their own particular research focus and interests. The details are given in the respective sections below.

One methodological point applies to all twelve personas: the descriptions provided in the prompt were deliberately minimal. Whatever additional theological characteristics emerge in the LLM responses should therefore be understood as a product of the models’ own elaboration, drawn from their training data, rather than as a consequence of detailed prompting. This has direct implications for how the responses are interpreted throughout this paper.

4.2.1 Muslim Personas

Next to the baseline “Muslim”, Professor Svensson chose the following five personas: “a Sunni scholar trained at al-Azhar University”, “a Shiite *mujtahid* trained in Qom”, “a Salafi scholar trained at the University of Madina”, “an independent progressive Muslim theologian”, and “Mahmoud Muhammad Taha, founder of the Sudanese Republican Brothers”. The following was the basis for the choice.

The historical division is represented by two personas drawn from the two main branches of Islam. Al-Azhar in Cairo and the *hawza* in Qom are two of the most prestigious centres of Islamic learning in the Sunni and Shiite traditions respectively. Mujtahid (a person performing *ijtihad*, i.e. interpretation of the scriptures) is a specific Shī‘a designation for a trained religious scholar.

Salafism has been referred to as a “new religious movement” (Meijer 2009) in Islam that has gained considerable momentum internationally since the 1990s. It is characterized by a strict literalist approach, demanding a return to the beliefs and practices of the “pious forefathers” (*al-salaf al-salih*), usually understood as

the first three generations after the Prophet. Prototypical Salafism is well known for a confrontational theology, both towards adherents of other religions and towards other Muslims accused of “innovations” in belief and practice — such as saint veneration, which Salafis view as a deviation from pure monotheism. There is a close affinity between Salafism and the dominant religious ideology of Saudi Arabia, often referred to as Wahhabism, and the University of Medina is a principal centre of Salafi scholarship (Ridgeon 2015; Farquhar 2016; Lauzière 2010).

Progressive Islam, as this contemporary tendency is discussed in scholarship, is in many ways the theological opposite of Salafism, and in some respects a response to its spread. It is generally characterized as an inclusive tendency, focused on finding ways to incorporate values such as tolerance, pluralism, social justice, human rights, gender equality and non-discrimination into Islam through often innovative independent reinterpretation, emically claimed to be *ijtihad*. Unlike Salafism, progressive Islam has no clear institutional centre. Those identifying as “progressive” thinkers are typically university-educated scholars with academic positions, often at Western universities (Safi 2003; Duderija 2017). This institutional asymmetry — a well-defined centre for Salafi scholarship versus a diffuse, academically located progressive tendency — is itself potentially significant for how the models handle the two personas.

Mahmoud Muhammad Taha was executed for blasphemy in 1985, after having developed a radically new and mystically inspired approach to the Qur’ān and its interpretation, aimed at accommodating modernity, set out in *al-risala al-thaniya min al-islam* (The Second Message of Islam) (Mahmoud 2007; Thomas 2010).

4.2.2 Christian Personas

Next to the baseline “Christian”, Professor Radde-Antweiler chose the following five personas: “a Roman Catholic bishop from the Congo”, “a Roman Catholic bishop from the US”, “a Russian Orthodox priest from Moscow”, “a pastor from the New Creation Church, Singapore”, and “Johann Caspar Lavater”. This choice was based on specific selection criteria.

The selection of Christian personas aimed to combine positions of authority with intra-theological diversity. All personas hold recognized positions of authority within their respective traditions, though the foundation of this authority differs fundamentally. Some personas (both Roman Catholic bishops, the Russian

Orthodox priest) derive their authority from traditional ecclesiastical offices such as bishop, priest, or pastor, where authority is conferred through institutional structures, ordination, and hierarchical appointment within the church. In contrast, other personas such as Johann Caspar Lavater possess knowledge-based authority as theological scholars, where authority stems from academic credentials, scholarly publications, and intellectual contributions to theological discourse rather than from formal church office. This distinction allows us to examine whether LLMs respond differently to institutional versus intellectual authority figures.

A second general criterion was Christian doctrinal diversity. To represent that, distinctions were made between Roman Catholic, Protestant, and Russian Orthodox positions. In the case of Protestantism, an even stronger distinction was drawn between Reformed (Lavater) and evangelical theologies (pastor from the New Creation Church). Regarding the latter, we were specifically interested in whether we can confirm studies by Kurlberg et al. (2026) that found a tendency to adopt evangelical content in Bible apps and AI.

Geographic variation was incorporated to investigate potential regional biases in LLM training data and to examine whether perspectives from certain countries might be overrepresented or privileged. Consequently, personas were distributed across North America, Africa, Asia, and Europe. The selection of specific countries reflected contemporary ecclesiastical significance.

In addition, two personas from the same religious tradition were selected to evaluate the reflection of recent media discussions: the Roman Catholic bishops from the United States and Congo were chosen because bishops from these countries gained considerable media visibility during recent papal conclaves. Public discussions about various candidates during papal elections — mostly based on certain stereotypes (e.g., that bishops from the Global South hold more conservative values and theologies) — can be observed. This enables examination of whether LLM outputs mirror these media narratives, potentially revealing insights into training data composition.

Additionally, a specific historical figure was selected: the eighteenth-century theologian Johann Caspar Lavater. Lavater is particularly distinguished by the fact that, after a classical Reformed theological education, he focused on the image of God in man: “Anyone, he believed, could in their earthly lifetime rouse the divine powers within them and attain the likeness of Christ” (Weigelt 2011). He became famous primarily for physiognomy (the study of the relationship

between a person’s physical appearance and their mental characteristics). With regard to interreligious dialogue, his writing “Letter to the Enlightened Jew” is particularly interesting because his public challenge to the Jewish philosopher Moses Mendelssohn (to either refute Christianity or be baptized) became highly disputed, and this debate is considered a milestone in the history of Jewish emancipation and interreligious dialogue. Furthermore, only limited digital data about him is available online, which may enable verification of whether this leads to hallucinations in LLMs.

4.3 A Note on Language Choice

All interactions with the LLMs were conducted in English, and the prompt was in English throughout. This choice was motivated by several considerations. English is the dominant language in the training data of all major LLMs, and prompting in English maximizes the likelihood of rich, well-elaborated responses across all four models, regardless of potential differences in their respective strengths in other languages. Furthermore, using a single language across all models, all personas, and both channels is a prerequisite for systematic comparison. Introducing language as an additional variable would have multiplied the size of the dataset considerably, and is better left for future, more targeted studies. There is ongoing research into whether language choice in prompts influences output. Some findings based on earlier, less capable models indicate that it does, but a recent replication using more powerful LLMs concludes that the effects are minimal and negligible (Sun and Wang 2025). It should nevertheless be noted that the English-language framing is a limitation of the current dataset, and one that is particularly worth flagging given that the Muslim and Christian personas represent traditions in which other languages — such as Arabic, Persian, Urdu, Russian or Latin — carry significant theological and textual weight. The extent to which prompting in a language other than English would produce different results remains an open question, and one that the current dataset is not designed to answer.

5. The Collection Procedure

We used the exact same prompt for both the API and the WebUI interactions with all four models mentioned above. The reasons for using both channels, and the methodological implications of differences between them, are discussed above.

Given the stochastic nature of LLM responses, a single request per persona per model per channel would not adequately capture the variation in possible outputs. We therefore submitted each prompt ten times (in the dataset marked as “runs”) per persona, per mode, and per channel. This number was chosen to balance dataset manageability against the need for sufficient variation to support both quantitative and qualitative analysis.

5.1 Specific Notes on the WebUI Interaction

The WebUI data collection took place during the period August 15–22, 2025. Testing via WebUI was conducted within the default web environment of each model using anonymous browser windows to ensure that responses were not influenced by any prior conversational context. The free-of-charge versions of the chatbots were used in the experiment. When the limits of the conversation were reached, the researcher waited for a new free time slot to continue the prompting. Furthermore, the temperature was set at its default values. The thinking mode feature was not activated but search was. The models were prompted to stay in their answers as close to 500 tokens as possible without interrupting the thought chain. This approach addressed issues identified during the pre-testing phase. It ensured that response lengths remained consistent and did not shorten over successive rounds, and prevented outputs from being interrupted mid-sentence.

Responses to prompts were copied and saved in an Excel sheet that was later shared with all other members of the research team. A specific outcome of the WebUI conversations was the case of role-play of the Salafi scholar, where the Claude Sonnet 4 model repeatedly refused to play the role. The issue was solved by putting the prompt into the continuation of the previous conversation chat. Yet, the obtained responses were very specific in format (paragraph-structured, bullet-list-like format), and stylistics (backing its argumentation by initial claims like “Based on available academic information ...”). These responses thus exhibited notable stylistic and structural differences compared to other outputs in the experiment.

5.2 Specific Notes on the API Interaction

All data from the API interaction was collected over one day, September 1, 2025. Several technical settings possible in the API interaction, but not in the WebUI interaction, affect LLM responses and merit comment.

Regarding response length: we initially set a maximum output for the API responses to 500 tokens, with a view to processing responses using sentence embeddings, which are subject to token limitations. This proved to be a mistake, as some responses were cut off mid-answer. We therefore removed the length restriction and ran the collection again, allowing the models to determine response length. Sub-datasets from individual models where responses were cut off have been saved, but do not appear in the final dataset.

Regarding temperature: this setting in the API regulates the degree of randomness in the model's token selection. At a temperature of 0, the model always selects the most probable next token; higher temperatures introduce more variation. Test runs with three settings — 0, maximum, and a middle value — produced noticeably different results. However, incorporating temperature as a systematic variable would have substantially increased the size of the dataset and the complexity of the analysis. We therefore chose to use the middle temperature setting across all models and all runs, and leave temperature as a variable for future research.

6. Some Notes on the Final Dataset

The final dataset comprises 960 responses and is available from <https://researchdata.se/en/catalogue/dataset/2026-94/1>. The dataset contains the name of the model, the channel, the date of data collection, the iteration number, and the model response.

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